

Trauma of Work Place of Females: A Study of Sefi Atta's *Swallow*

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Abstract

This study explores the impact of workplace sexual assault, highlighting the debilitating effects on psychological, social, physical, career trajectories and overall wellbeing of the victims. Gendered sexual assault at workplace is a menacing and prevalent issue that distresses the female workers across various professions. The research exposes how Sefi Atta's characters navigate through the complexities of trauma and highlights the relationship between trauma, gender and power utilizing the workplace milieu. The selected novel for the study is examined using qualitative method of information analysis. The study used trauma theory to expose the distress and devastation sexual assault victims experience. The research discovered that women are not safe at workplaces due to patriarchy. It observes that power dynamics and organizational notions enhance the silencing of the victims and the propagation of the offense. Considering the devastating effects of sexual assault, the study recommends that more efforts should be made by literary writers, the masses and the government to identify interventions and strategies for addressing the menace and overriding consequences of sexual assault by promoting healing and resilience among survivors.

Key Words: Gender, Patriarchy, Workplace, Sexual assault and Trauma.

Introduction

Several assaults occur in various forms at work place. Such assaults occur in form of religious, racial, gender, nationality and sexual assaults. Sexual assault is one of the major negative work experiences of employees especially on the side of the female folk. Though it also occurs against the male gender, it is minimal compared to its malignant occurrences against females. This involves any form of sexual advances that debases, threatens and leaves one uncomfortable. Despite the enormity of the crime of sexual assault, it tends to attract less attention among other challenges of women at work place. This may be because of the usual concealment by the abused due to fear, shame, stigmatization and other cultural constraints on open discussion of sex issues. This act which sometimes is deliberately targeted causes emotional distress on the victim. Women do not deserve such emotional distress because the economic role they play in families cannot be overemphasized. Their position in the society is very strategic due to the numerous roles they play to all genders such as reproduction, emotional balancing and socialization. Several of them nowadays are the sole financiers of their families. Yet, despite the enormous demand on them at home, several of them still combine their home work with office workload so as to make ends meet. Sequel to these demands on women, they require a very conducive atmosphere at work place so as to effectively be productive. However, the needed peaceful work environment is a mirage in several workplaces because so many women face all manner of discriminatory attitude from their male counterpart because of gender, racism or superiority. These have variously been reported by many writers who, like crusaders, campaign against the odds in the society. For instance, according to Equal Employment Opportunity Commission (2016) “Sexual harassment is often trivialized or dismissed as ‘just joking around’, rather than being recognized as a form of sex discrimination (Equal Employment Right, 2016, p.124).” The occurrence of sexual harassment and assault in the workplace is overwhelming. The above report states that the offence is often treated with levity and not as severely as the matter deserves.

Depictions of Sexual Assault at Work Place

Sefi Atta is one of the crusaders who explored the gruesome effect of sexual assault at work place. In her novel, *Swallow*, she presents Mr. Salako, a branch and most senior manager in the banking industry who is in the habit of assaulting the ladies in the establishment. He does so by either grabbing their waists or their hands or tickling their palms. Rose has often complained to her friend, Tolani that he

passes comments about her body. According to *Legal Voice Toward Justice and Gender* (2024), a work place assaulter is one that does any of the following; casts unwelcome sexually suggestive remarks about a lady's body, demands for dates, makes offensive gestures and touches, presents intimidating character and exposes pornographic materials to a targeted person. Rose had been dismissing and rejecting advances from her boss, Mr. Salako, though the advances already draws the attention of the bank personnel who view her with contempt and distrust. She undergoes Mr Salako's abuses but at the point he tries hugging her, she pushes him away (7). Women face sexual assault mainly from their superior male colleagues. This brings about all manner of hostility and abusing power over a female victim because of her refusal to yield to the mischievous sexual advances.

Furthermore, because of the female victims' ignorance or fear, many of them either have to endure the harassment or have job termination stare them on the face. Such is the fate of Rose who is either ignorant of legal processes or is scared to utilize the facility. She slaps Mr. Salako and calls him "bloody bastard" in the banking hall at such misdemeanors. She must have done this out of anger and probably, in her bid to exonerate herself from the gossip of her colleagues. Her keeping quiet in whatever kind of open assault in the banking hall, at the full glare of both colleagues and customers would have been a confirmation that she is his girlfriend as have been gossiped in the firm. Rose's reaction warranted her immediate sack from job. Mr. Salako is concerned about his prestige as a man, superior officer and even the overall manager of the bank branch being slapped publicly but never thought of the open assault he usually subjected Rose, his subordinate to. Little did he think of the fact that he has been belittling himself before his subordinate. The report of National Institute of Justice (2016) states as follows, "Research has shown that perpetrators of sexual assault often target individuals who are vulnerable...The prestige or status of the victim does not appear to be a factor in the perpetrator's decision to commit the assault (National Institute of Justice, 2016, p. 20-22)." The prestige of the assaulted, either before or after the assault never matters to the predators nor do they consider the psychological, health and social implications of this heinous act. Rebecca Campbell reviews that "Research has shown that perpetrators of sexual assault often exhibit a lack of empathy for their victims and a disregard for the harm they cause. In fact, many perpetrators report that they do not feel remorse or guilt for their actions (3)." Such is the state of Mr. Salako who thought less of the feelings of his prey, but rather adds more pain to them. Franka, the office gossip, already refers to Mr. Salako as Rose's boy- friend owing to the previous attitudes of Mr. Salako towards Rose. Franka asks Tolani,

Haven't you heard? "Rose", she said. "Her boyfriend, Salako has finally sacked her" (8). It is obvious that the colleagues have been witnessing the inordinate touches and comments but instead of frowning at the predator, they lash it out on Rose, the prey. Hakeem thought Rose to be a bad parented lady as he states "Yes, I 'hexpected' it sooner or later, it was a matter of time. That woman does not know 'ow' to control 'erself' and Salako 'as been letting her get away with it. Noow, see what she's gone and done, disgracing 'im in public like small boy..." (8). The incident becomes the story of the day in the office, so many versions going round, all implicating Rose as the culprit. Victim blaming is one of the negative responses to the victims of sexual assault. Citron presents that the game of blaming the victim often tends to exonerate the predator from the crime. Citron (2014) states that "Victim-blaming rhetoric is often used to shift the focus away from the perpetrator's actions and onto the victim's behavior. Thereby excusing o justifying the assault (Citron, 2014, p.457)". One of such stories is that "Rose tore Mr. Salako's shirt in the banking hall and the security guards dragged her out of the building, and they set their Alsatians on her, and it bit Rose... (9)". The above scenario confirms the stance of Stanko Elizebeth in "Wife Battering: All in the Family" that sexual assault is "unwanted sexual attention. Its behavioural forms are many and include visual, verbal; unwanted pressures for sexual favour or date; unwanted touching or pinching, with implied threats of job-related consequences for non-cooperation; physical assault; sexual assault, rape" (91). She opines that these happen because of their power within the workplaces where men usually assume higher status and are ready to both hire and fire women at will. Rose, having been sacked, resorted to drinking and sleeping, Tolani reported it this way, "Rose drank more than usual" (38). ..."She was drinking beer like water now, drinking and falling asleep" (41). Anteghini et al (2002) suggests that alcoholism, smoking of harmful substances and abuse of drugs are inclusive in the life challenges of sexually abused victims. These life challenges and illicit life behaviours often lead to life-lasting or even terminal health challenges.

The Trauma of Work Place Sexual Assault of Females in Sefi Atta's *Swallow*

Depression is one of the consequences of sexual assault, whereas the predator goes on with his own life, the prey languishes psychologically, financially and health wise. As Tolani encouraged her to get new job, she blurted out her phobia for job, "Me, work? So someone like Salako can harass me again? Over my dead body" (47). She finds office work dreadfully disgusting because of the awful experience she has. Matsushita-arao (2007) asserts in that some of the symptoms of depression are "prolonged

sadness, feelings of hopelessness, unexplained crying, loss of energy or loss of interest and pleasure in activities previously enjoyed” (Matsushita-arao, 2007, p.66). This is to say that depression often attacks someone’s entire attitude and this may equally lead to one’s feeling of hopelessness. The extremity of such depressive attitude is suicidal thoughts and attempts. This terrible experience beclouds Rose’s vision that she imagines that all offices are filled with whores and all men, birds of a feather. She forgets her effort to make livelihood through working hard, she rather lost interest in job and vowed never to seek for another job.

At the announcement by Alhaji Umar that Tolani was being transferred downstairs to replace Rose in Mr. Salako’s office, Tolani’s first imagination of Mr. Salako is “his plump fingers tickling my palms” (30). She laments that she is being transferred to a war zone. Indeed, it is a war zone because sexual assault is quite a battle between the predator and the prey. Reskin (1993) presents that women are often subject to this assault because men use their exalted positions against them. They conclude that power imbalances is one of the significant reasons men are usually the initiators and perpetrators of the assault. Tolani starts work and faces the same ordeal from Mr Salako. She reports her own case as follows,

“He walked between the desk and the cabinet. I tried to get out of his way but got stuck in the narrow space. I had my back to him. Mr. Salako’s arms came round my waist”.

“S’cuse me, he grunted.”

“I lifted my arms higher to free myself and he hugged me tighter. I lowered my arms. Mr Salako was rubbing his pelvis against me. I pushed him back so hard his desk moved” (55).

Sexual assault at workplace can hurt the health and wellbeing of workers. It can make workers to be less productive and increase employee absenteeism and turnover. Kessier (2016) that “Sexual harassment and assault can have significant economic costs for individuals and organizations, including reduced productivity, increased absenteeism and decreased job satisfaction .” (Kessier, 2016, 437) After the above incidence in Mr Salako’s office, Franka, the office gossip who entered the office unannounced during the incidence carries the story around that she witnessed Tolani’s love affairs with Mr. Daudu and Mr. Salako. Tolani’s mood is affected. She stops talking to everyone and even develops stomach cramps on hearing Mr. Salako’s voice laughing on phone, the cramps become stronger whenever he calls her name. She refuses searching for file for Mr. Salako and he serves her a query. In

answering the query, she divulges the secret of her assault, yet no action is taken, rather she is instructed to re-type the answer (77). She keeps to herself as a device to ward off gossip. The impact of sexual assault is real and damaging. Tangney and Dearing (2002) assert that rape victims often exhibit behavioural self-blame which is an attitude linked with emotions of guilt within the enclave of rape victims. This usually results in shame and inferiority complex.. Tolani faced shame and stigmatization. Employees that experience sexual assault can often suffer depression, stress and anxiety, sleeplessness, weight loss or gain and reputation problem. Tolani even blames herself for not confronting Mr. Salako and reasoned whether it is her fault for wearing ‘sexy shoes and fashionable clothes’ (57). The above feeling of Tolani agrees with the opinion of Matsushita-arao (2007) that most victims who experience behavioural self-blame reason that they should have done something differently and, therefore, feel at fault. They also experience self-blame because they feel there is something naturally wrong with them which have caused them to deserve to be assaulted. Furthermore, Tolani remembers having her clothes raised up by a boy in primary school and her teacher had to question how she was walking when it happened (57).

Archart-Treichel (2005) states that the enormity of psychological effects of sexual assault is summarized in Post- Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) which is a “mental health disorder that is triggered by a terrifying event” ((Archart-Treichel, 2007, 337). Among the symptoms of PTSD, he lists nightmares, flashbacks, prolonged depression and uncontrollable thoughts about the event. The uncontrollable thought about the assault leads her down memory lane to recollect the seemingly childhood assault and the blame on her for the action. Sexual assault is usually blamed on the victim as if she did a thing she ought not to have done whereas in actual sense, the fault is not really theirs. The victims are often judged harshly for being passive because they are expected to respond in a more assertive manner. Stigmatization which leads to shame, guilt and self- blame is portrayed by Sarah Ullma in “Sexual Assault and Stigma: A Systematic Review” as part of the consequences of sexual assault that often retards the victim’s ability of quick recovery and hinders the survivor from neither seeking assistance nor revealing the event.

In addition to psychological consequence of sexual assault, Campbell and Raja (2008) present that there is also social perspectives of sexual assault. In their view, they refer to sociological effect as “secondary victimization” (262). They state that the “secondary victimization of a sexually assaulted victim is the

re-traumatization of the victim through the responses of individuals or situations” (262). They further explain that blaming, inappropriate address and improper use of language on the victim by family relations, medical practitioners or some other firms that the victim contacts are regarded as forms of secondary victimization. Sexual assault stigmatizes, so any attitude or unwarranted reference to the victim amounts to re-traumatization. The jest of Tolani’s colleagues for her daring to raise an eyebrow about the assault and even terming her promiscuous amounts to re-victimization. Sexual assault can also affect the observers of the assault and not only the assaulted. They may suffer mental or physical harm which decreases their work morale. Franka’s tale bearing of the assault all around the office stigmatizes Tolani, makes her unstable to function accurately and also distracts the coordination of other staff at work and all these hampers productivity.

According to Legal Voice towards Justice and Gender Liberation (2024), hostility in work environment occurs when an employer or superior discriminates in hiring procedures due to sexual advances on one. This occurs in ways as denial of promotion, delay or reduction of wages, denial of vacation and its benefits, strictness in discipline and termination terms. Tolani experiences the above assertion. She suffers denial and helplessness as Mr. Salaku refuses her going on vacation which she badly needed so as to ease off the effects of the assault (127). Solako plays smart as he does not lay off Tolani immediately she reports him. He allowed time so as it would not be related to Rose’s case. The dreams of the two girls that hitherto worked hard to alleviate poverty become thwarted as the two become sexually harassed and sacked by the same man.

Previously, Tolani confessed her fears of personal hopelessness in the country, Nigeria. She states, “Normally, I pretended not to see beggars. It was almost like seeing my future” (9) Atta x-rays the nature of poverty and economic hardship in the nation. However, Tolani is made to face the same future she feared and envisaged through sexual assault which leaves her financially incapacitated. Her career becomes threatened as she is blacklisted and has no chance of receiving a worthy recommendation from the bank. The bankruptcy makes her become a prey to O.C’s lure through Rose owing to the despair and trauma of Mr. Salako’s assault. The quest for surviving the socio-economic hardship culminates to Rose’s decision and conviction of Tolani to accept the drug deal which terminates Rose’s life. Tolani initially, objects the idea of drug trafficking but succumbs to Rose’s enticement with the conviction that everybody is corrupt, starting from the head of state. She states thus, “Our heads of state steal, our

boards of directors steal. Who asks where their money comes from? People praise them. They run after them to spread some of their wealth. I am tired of being poor (139). Atta seems to focalize that women are the most vulnerable and easily victimized both socially and economically because of their gender. The debilitating economic effect of sexual assault on the duo becomes inestimable. Rose's death portends an affirmation of the debilitating condition patriarchal society places women. Women are used and dumped as indispensable tools.

Atta explores the duo's ability to fight sexual assault at their own capacity defying the consequences. They utilize different avenues to fight their courses. Rose uses her will-power resistance while Tolani follows official due process of formal report. Tolani had earlier boasted to slap any man that messes up on her by inordinate touches, however, at this juncture, she leaves Salako's office like an obedient daughter would. By the foregoing, Atta seizes the opportunity to present the confusion and incapacitation of most sexually assaulted victims at the point of attack. Rose summoned courage for action after several assaults and even at that, the entire workforce lend their voice against her action, even Tolani projected that Salako would sack Rose and nobody would talk. Mr. Ignatius had to threaten Tolani of the dire consequence of her report not minding that it would be torn to pieces. Atta explores the high-handedness of patriarchy by the way the two friends get fired from job and how the system favours and encourages the perpetrators to remain in their barbaric deeds.

Amidst alternations of life, Atta presents Tolani as a survivor who passes through economic difficulties occasioned by the patriarchal subjugation and oppression. Their job terminations mark a turning point in their lives. Rose's hoodwinking and death through her association with a drug baron would have been avoided was she still on employment. Tolani resorts to joining her mother in the cloth dying business. Rose and Tolani are victims of workplace sexual assaults but they are made to feel otherwise. This is sad reality of many victims, having to quit their jobs or stay silent while enduring such harassment. Rose is a fearless and tough young woman and poverty occasioned by workplace sexual assault pushed her to such extreme decision that cost her life. Tolani gets a second chance of life and now has a new perspective on how she wants her life to be.

Conclusion

Sefi Atta's *Swallow* has a task to accomplish. Attah's duty as a literary artist and a crusader is to draw the attention of all and sundry, especially the managers of establishments, to the gory circumstances of gendered sexual assault in offices and the traumatic challenges emanating from such affairs. This paper discusses psychological, social, and economic consequences of gendered sexual assault as observed from the selected work for this research. The violations the characters experience, seriously affect their mental balances. Most of the assaulted girls have accumulated psychological traumatic imbalances that lead to the life-threatening decisions they take. The traumatic disorder accruing from these uninvited incidents the girls face devastates them and leave them with unaccomplished dreams.

Recommendations

Considering the devastating and deadly effects of workplace sexual assault on the female survivors, the study recommends that gender sensitive strategies for understanding and addressing sexual assault at workplace should be utilized by organizations for addressing the menace of sexual assault. Furthermore, establishments ought to prioritize the formation of harmless and supportive work environments that encourage gender equality and also promote healing and resilience among survivors.

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